

D1.4 Final report on the external and direct support provision and lessons learned

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AIDV	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation
API	Application Programming Interface
D	Deliverable
DCAT	Data Catalogue vocabulary
DCAT-AP	DCAT Application Profile
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GA	Grant Agreement
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
I-ADOPT	Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology
IDW	International Data Week
IG	Interest Group
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
IPCC AR7	IPCC Seventh Assessment Report
maDMP	Machine actionable data management plan
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGC-OM Standard	OGC Observations and Measurements Standard
PID	Persistent Identifier
PRO4RS	Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software
RDA	Research Data Alliance
WG	Working Group
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

The RDA TIGER project aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of Research Data Alliance Working Groups by providing targeted direct and external support to increase the impact of WG outputs on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), global Open Science practices, and researchers, data professionals and the society at large. Across the project lifetime (1 January 2023 – 31 December 2025), RDA TIGER awarded 32 grants benefiting 19 RDA WGs.

Under its Grant Agreement, RDA TIGER delivered three main types of direct and external support:

1. Minor grants meant for travel purposes for key WG personnel to participate in the WG meetings;
2. Hiring of external experts for specific tasks as defined by the WGs;
3. Grants given directly to a 3rd party to support the actual main activities of the WG using the Financial Support to Third Parties (i.e. cascade grant) mechanism.

This deliverable provides an overview of the different direct and external support mechanisms within RDA TIGER and how they were managed by the project, in particular by WP1. The deliverable provides statistics on each direct and external support mechanism, the impact of these mechanisms on RDA WGs and the broader EOSC and Open Science landscape, and lessons learned from the implementation of these mechanisms.

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1. Introduction: External and Direct Support Mechanisms in RDA TIGER

The RDA TIGER project provided a number of external and direct support mechanisms to Research Data Alliance Working Groups (RDA WGs) with the objective to increase their efficiency and to maximise the impact of their outputs on the European Open Science Cloud, global Open Science practices, and researchers, data professionals and the society at large. RDA TIGER Grant Agreement (GA) defined three categories of external and direct support provided by the project to RDA WGs; these included: (1) Grants given directly to a 3rd party to support the actual main activities of the WG using the Financial Support to Third Parties (i.e. cascade grant) mechanism; (2) Minor grants meant for travel purposes for key WG personnel to participate in the WG meetings; (3) Hiring of external experts for specific tasks as defined by the WGs.¹ RDA TIGER deliverable D1.1 Guidelines for Support Management² provided further categorisation of the external and direct support mechanisms by differentiating between grants provided directly to RDA WG members (subdivided to reimbursements of travel costs and direct purchases for the use of WG members) and grants provided for the benefit of WGs (subdivided to in-kind services provided by RDA TIGER project staff, services provided via external service contract, service provided via subcontracting contract, and services provided via a 3rd party contract).³

This deliverable does not cover in-kind support services provided by RDA TIGER project staff to RDA WGs, which included the Communication Service, the Engagement and Landscape Service, the Output Support Service and the Facilitation Service. These services and the related lessons learned are discussed in dedicated deliverables.⁴

RDA TIGER awarded 32 grants to deliver its external and direct support mechanism in the lifetime of the project, from 1 January 2023 to 31 December 2025. The applications received and grants awarded via the different support mechanisms are summarised in Table 1:

¹ RDA TIGER GA 101094406, Part B, p. 7 .

² Asmi, A. (2023). D1.1 Guidelines for Support Management (1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>

³ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 6-7.

⁴ Please refer to the RDA TIGER deliverable D2.4 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877228>) for an overview of the Communication Service provision and lessons learned, the RDA TIGER deliverable D3.5 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877303>) for the final report on Engagement and Landscape monitoring and lessons learned, the RDA TIGER deliverable D4.3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17762711>) for the final report on the lessons learned from providing Output Support Services, and the RDA TIGER deliverable D5.3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877424>) for the final evaluation of the Facilitation Services based on feedback and QA/QC actions.

Table 1: RDA TIGER External and Direct Support Mechanisms

External or direct support mechanism	Time period available	Number of applications received	Number of external and direct support grants awarded
Grants provided to RDA WG members	2023-2025	32	16
a) Travel reimbursements (i.e. travel grants)	2023-2025	30	14
b) Workshops	2023-2025	2	2
Grants provided to RDA WGs to hire external experts	2023-2025	14	9
Grants provided via Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) mechanism to support RDA WGs	2024-2025	35	7
Totals	2023-2025	81	32

As per the deliverable D1.1, all grants to provide external and direct support mechanisms were approved by the RDA TIGER Selection Committee⁵. The Selection Committee evaluated applications received from RDA WG members and/or RDA WGs in response to RDA TIGER Open Calls, Calls for RDA TIGER Travel Grants and Calls for RDA TIGER Cascade Grants. The calls and the approval and delivery procedures for each external and direct support mechanism is discussed in greater detail below.

2. Direct Support to RDA Working Group members

Direct support to RDA WG members was intended to support individual WG members in their tasks for the WGs. The deliverable D1.1 foresaw two kinds of direct support for RDA WG members: (1) travel reimbursements and (2) workshop costs (e.g. costs for meeting room, catering, A/V equipment).⁶ This aligns with RDA TIGER GA that foresaw minor grants for RDA WG members as part of the direct and external support mechanisms.⁷ The budget

⁵ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 5.

⁶ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 8.

⁷ RDA TIGER Grant Agreement 101094406, Part B, p. 7

categories foreseen to deliver direct support included *C1. Travel and Subsistence* and/or *C3. Other goods and services*; no personnel costs could be claimed.⁸

Direct support to RDA WG members was administered in line with the rules defined in deliverable D.1.1.⁹ RDA WGs were able to apply for direct support via the continuously open RDA TIGER Open Call¹⁰ (see also Annex 1), with submission review deadlines by the Selection Committee every 3 months from May 2023 to August 2025. In addition, RDA TIGER opened two dedicated Travel Grant calls for RDA WG members to attend, in-person, the RDA Plenary 25 in Brisbane, Australia in October 2025; these two calls had application deadlines in June 2025 and August 2025¹¹ (see also Annex 1). The Selection Committee referred to the evaluation criteria defined in RDA TIGER deliverable D6.1, also included in the call texts, as well as the available budget communicated to the Selection Committee by WP1 to select the grantees receiving direct support. The Selection Committee decisions were communicated to applicants by WP6; successful applicants were then contacted by WP1 to inform them about practicalities and proceed with grant preparation (e.g. preparation of the travel grant reimbursement agreements, information about reporting requirements). WP1 also supported the delivery of direct support by responding to grantees' questions and by ensuring that grants were administered in line with RDA TIGER internal rules and Horizon Europe rules. The Travel Grants to RDA WG members and grants for workshop delivery were administered with dedicated procedures, described below.

2.1 Travel Grants to RDA WG Members

RDA TIGER opened two dedicated calls for travel grants (see Annex 1). Both calls targeted RDA WG members who had sessions accepted at the International Data Week 2025/ RDA Plenary 25 in Brisbane, Australia and aimed to attend the conference in person. The twice-yearly RDA Plenaries provide a space for RDA WGs to come together through dedicated working sessions to present intermediary and final outputs as well as on-going activities, and to gather feedback from the community in order to fine-tune and further improve the quality and relevance of their outputs. In the life-cycle of a RDA WG, the RDA Plenaries are key events: sessions at Plenaries are key working meetings for RDA WGs and usually also mark milestones in WG work plans. In case of in-person plenaries like the RDA Plenary 25 in Brisbane, Australia, and as mandated by RDA rules, at least one RDA WG

⁸ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, pp. 6-7, 9.

⁹ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 9.

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/open-call-rda-working-group-facilitation-support/>

¹¹ Lehtsalu, L., Delipalta, A., O'Connor, R., Heikkurinen, M., & van Reterghem, T. (2023–2025). RDA TIGER Direct and External Support Mechanisms Supporting Documentation [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431>

co-chair is required to be present in-person at the plenary for the group’s session to run.¹² Direct support to RDA WG members to attend International Data Week 2025/ RDA Plenary 25 facilitated RDA WG members’ participation at these key working meetings and contributed to the efficiency of these RDA WGs in the delivery of their expected outputs.

The two calls for travel grants received a total of 30 applications and resulted in 14 travel grants awarded. Table 2 below provides an overview of RDA TIGER Travel Grant Calls.

Table 2: RDA TIGER Travel Grant Calls

Call	Applications Received	Travel Grants awarded	Travel Grants accepted	RDA WGs which members accepted travel grants
1st call	14	10	9	FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG, Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG, Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive Data WG, Complex Citations WG, AIDV WG, Common maDMP API WG, Data Repository Attributes WG, Building Immune Digital Twins WG
2nd call	16	4	3	Health Data GORC Profile WG, Common maDMP API WG, AIDV WG
Totals	30	14	12	9 RDA WGs

RDA TIGER Travel Grants were administered as travel reimbursements, reimbursing up to 1,500.00 euro of the successful applicants' eligible travel costs (registration fees, transportation and accommodation costs, as outlined in the two calls). Successful applicants received an information sheet with practical and procedural details¹³ (see also Annex 1). A travel reimbursement agreement¹⁴ (see also Annex 1) was signed between grantees and RDA Association AISBL, RDA TIGER coordinator and WP1 lead. The agreement established grant

¹² This was communicated to co-chairs of groups in the acceptance note of their WG session. See an example here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/posts/?post=189805>

¹³ RDA TIGER Direct and External Support Mechanisms Supporting Documentation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431>

¹⁴ RDA TIGER Direct and External Support Mechanisms Supporting Documentation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431>

sum, responsibilities and reimbursement procedures; the latter were in line with the expected procedure outlined in the deliverable D1.1.¹⁵

Not all RDA TIGER Travel Grant recipients were able to accept their award. This was because they were unable to secure the additional funds necessary to cover the full cost of travel to Brisbane, Australia.

2.2 Workshop Costs for RDA WG Members

Through Open Calls, RDA TIGER also provided direct support to workshops organised by RDA WGs.

One RDA WG - the I-ADOPT WG - used this opportunity to organise both a hack-a-thon challenge as well as two workshops, submitting two separate applications to two different Open Call deadlines. The Selection Committee approved both applications for funding because both the hack-a-thon challenge¹⁶ as well as the two workshops¹⁷ supported the further adoption and standardisation of the WG's outputs.

As part of RDA TIGER support to the hack-a-thon, the project provided travel bursaries to hack-a-thon winners to attend the RDA Plenary 23 in Costa Rica in November 2024 where the hack-a-thon results would be presented during a dedicated I-ADOPT WG session. As the winners were not able to travel, RDA TIGER agreed to cover the fee for their remote participation in the dedicated I-ADOPT WG session at RDA Plenary 23. This support for the hack-a-thon was administered as travel grants (reimbursements).

The two I-ADOPT workshops, held in Vienna in spring 2025, received support from RDA TIGER to cover workshop organisation and WG members travel costs to the workshop. To administer direct support to these two workshops, RDA Association AISBL established a subcontracting agreement with a co-chair of the I-ADOPT WG that covered the relevant workshop preparation and delivery, including travel costs of the RDA WG members attending the workshops; the co-chair was responsible for reporting on behalf of RDA WG members participating in the workshops and submitting a single financial report.

In addition to the direct support to workshops via the Open Call, one of the RDA TIGER Pilot WGs, the RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG that had

¹⁵ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, pp. 8-9.

¹⁶ <https://i-adopt.github.io/challenge.html>

¹⁷ <https://i-adopt.github.io/workshops.html>

been pre-selected for RDA TIGER support as part of the RDA TIGER project proposal, held a one-day workshop co-located with RDA Plenary 20 in Gothenburg, Sweden in March 2023. The organisation of this co-located workshop was financially and administratively supported by RDA TIGER. This direct support provision was not carried through an Open Call, as the WG support had been pre-approved as part of the RDA TIGER Grant Agreement.

2.3 Impact of the Grants provided directly to RDA Working Group members

RDA TIGER approved direct support to 11 RDA WGs: co-chairs and members of 9 RDA WGs received travel reimbursements to attend the International Data Week 2025/ RDA Plenary 25, 1 RDA WG received support for workshop organisation, which also included covering travel costs of the WG members, and 1 further RDA WG that was included as a Pilot WG in RDA TIGER received support for workshop organisation.

The RDA WG that received workshop support – the RDA I-ADOPT WG – developed the I-ADOPT Framework Ontology as its output. The framework ontology, aims to facilitate interoperability between existing variable description models,¹⁸ was endorsed as a RDA Recommendation in 2022¹⁹ and is currently under consideration for becoming an extension in the OGC OM standard²⁰. The I-ADOPT WG hack-a-thon challenge²¹ and two variable modelling workshops²² were a critical step towards I-ADOPT Framework standardisation as part of OGC OM. As such, RDA TIGER direct support to I-ADOPT WG contributed to standardisation of a RDA Recommendation and harmonisation and alignment of Open Science technologies across EOSC and globally, which are the aims of RDA TIGER. Moreover, the I-ADOPT hack-a-thon challenge and the two variable modelling workshops attracted over 50 participants, including participants new to the I-ADOPT Framework Ontology. This supported further dissemination of the framework and its exploitation by data professionals.

The RDA GORC International Model WG, the Pilot WG that received direct support to organise a workshop, held a co-located workshop²³ at the RDA Plenary 20 in Gothenburg, Sweden in March 2023. During this hands-on workshop GORC attributes were refined,

¹⁸ <https://i-adopt.github.io/>

¹⁹ Magagna, B., Moncoiffé, G., Devaraju, A., Stoica, M., Schindler, S., Pamment, A., & RDA I-ADOPT WG. (2022). Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT) WG Outputs and Recommendations (1.1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00071>

²⁰ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/om/>

²¹ <https://i-adopt.github.io/challenge.html>

²² <https://i-adopt.github.io/workshops.html>

²³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/posts/?post=98391>

resulting in the recommendation model²⁴. The RDA GORC International Model is an impactful output, widely adopted across Europe, including being currently under consideration to support the EOSC Nodes.

Figure 1. RDA GORC International Model WG synthesis workshop funded and supported by RDA TIGER in Gothenburg, Sweden in March 2023.

The individual RDA WG members who received travel reimbursements to attend the International Data Week 2025/ RDA Plenary 25 were all co-chairs or active members of RDA WGs. Their presence at the International Data Week/ RDA Plenary 25 ensured the delivery of their WGs' plenary sessions, which present key milestones in those WG work plans. Moreover, since the International Data Week/ RDA Plenary 25 took place in Brisbane, Australia and attracted the attendance of a strong cohort of researchers and data professionals from the Asia, Australia and Oceania regions, sessions at the conference permitted RDA WG members, and by extension their WGs, to connect with practitioners in those regions, receive input, test and validate both intermediary as well as final results. Such exchanges support global alignment, harmonisation and standardisation of Open Science technologies and practices, which is an overarching aim of the RDA TIGER project.

The RDA TIGER travel support for Plenary attendance also enabled 1 person from a LMIC country (Indonesia) to attend IDW 2025, supporting broader engagement between RDA WGs and the broad extent of the RDA community. We awarded 2 travel grants to LMIC applicants, but the second recipient did not travel to the International Data Week/RDA Plenary 25 despite having initially accepted the grant.

2.4 Lessons Learned: Grants provided directly to RDA Working Group members

In the process of administering direct support to RDA WG members, the RDA TIGER project drew several lessons learned:

- **Communicate any restrictions to grants clearly and frequently** – RDA TIGER supported RDA Working Groups; within the RDA, there are also Interest Groups and

²⁴ Woodford, C., Treloar, A., Leggott, M., Payne, K., Jones, S., Lopez Albacete, J., Madalli, D., Genova, F., Dharmawardena, K., Chibhira, N., Åkerström, W. N., Macneil, R., Nurnberger, A., Pfeiffenberger, H., Tanifuji, M., Zhang, Q., Jones, N., Sesink, L., Wood-Charlson, E., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>

Communities of Practice. For the direct support that targeted individuals, i.e., RDA WG members, RDA TIGER received a number of applications from co-chairs and active members of RDA Interest Groups (IGs). Even though RDA TIGER communication throughout the project has been clear that RDA TIGER support is only for RDA WGs, as per our Grant Agreement, the fact that the Calls for Travel Grants, the 2nd call in particular, attracted a number of applicants from RDA IGs, evidences that communication about which groups and individuals are eligible to receive funding needs to be constant throughout the project.

- **Communicate any relevant eligibility conditions clearly and frequently** – RDA is a global organisation. RDA TIGER is a Horizon Europe project and its budget is subject to Horizon Europe eligibility rules. Despite our Calls for Travel Grants including a clarification of eligibility rules, we received several applications from countries ineligible to receive funding from Horizon Europe. When publishing a call that has a global reach, the eligibility rules need to be very clearly outlined.
- **Consider the desired impact as well as destination when determining the size of travel grants** – RDA TIGER Travel Grants provided RDA WG members up to a 1,500 euro reimbursement towards their travel expenses to International Data Week/ RDA Plenary 25. This was clearly communicated in the call texts, and applicants were also asked to outline their travel budget in the application form. Nevertheless, some successful applicants were later unable to accept the travel grant because they failed to secure the necessary additional funding to cover the full cost of travel to the International Data Week/ RDA Plenary 25. The sum per applicant made available may have been inadequate considering the location of the International Data Week/ RDA Plenary 25 in Brisbane, Australia. However, the project chose to prioritise supporting more individuals through smaller grants intended as supplementary to existing funding; given the location of IDW2025, providing full travel support would have significantly reduced the amount of individuals able to receive it.
- **High RDA community interest in funding** – Based on the response we saw to our calls for travel grants as well as Open Calls, we noted that RDA members, who mostly engage with RDA as volunteers, are eager to respond to available opportunities for funding.
- **A smooth administration of direct support through reimbursements** – Administratively, RDA TIGER project and the lead partner RDA Association AISBL managed direct support to RDA WG members through reimbursements. The process was clarified to all grantees after the award of the support by the Selection Committee, after which RDA Association AISBL put in place written award agreements with the grantees. Approached this way, administering direct support was a smooth process, even when managing all award agreements and reimbursement requests necessitated continued administrative effort from WP1.

3. External Support Provided to RDA Working Groups

RDA TIGER Grant Agreement foresaw two types of external support to RDA WGs: (a) grants given directly to a 3rd party to support the main activities of the WG using the Financial Support to Third Parties (i.e. cascade grant) mechanism and (b) hiring of external experts for specific tasks as defined by the WGs.²⁵ The deliverable D1.1, furthermore, considered the possibility that some of the RDA TIGER in-kind support services (i.e. Communication Service, the Engagement and Landscape Service, the Output Support Service and the Facilitation Service) could be offered by an external service contractor²⁶; after further clarification of the Horizon Europe rules, this type of external support was not introduced in the project. All RDA TIGER in-kind support services to RDA WGs were delivered by project partners, in accordance with the GA. This deliverable thus focuses on two types of external support that RDA TIGER made available to RDA WGs: External Expert Grants and Financial Support to Third Parties.

3.1 External Expert Grants

3.1.1 Selection Procedures and Management of the External Expert Grants

Deliverable D1.1 defined the scope of external expert grants as part of a broader definition of grants provided to Working Group members' benefit, indicating that such grants also included services requiring specific expertise or tools.²⁷ Deliverable D6.1 "Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee" provided further detail by defining these grants as subcontracting grants that "provide WGs with expertise or services that are beyond the capabilities, available time and/or resources available within the in-kind support provided by RDA TIGER."²⁸

RDA WGs were able to apply via the RDA TIGER Open Calls (see Annex 1), using Section C "Support for hiring external experts for the Working Group" of the RDA TIGER Support Services Application Form. Applicants were directed to use Section C if their RDA WG required specific expertise or a role that RDA TIGER could not cover through in-kind services. Applicants were also advised that RDA TIGER would either contract directly with an expert or launch an open call to find an expert, depending on the contents of their application (see Annex 1 for the RDA Open Call Application Form).

²⁵ RDA TIGER GA 101094406, Part B, p. 7.

²⁶ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 10.

²⁷ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 10.

²⁸ Rettberg, N. (2024). RDA TIGER D6.1 Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218371>, p. 10.

When considering Open Call applications that requested support for the hiring of external experts, the RDA TIGER Selection Committee focused on the added value of the external expert and their proposed work to the WG submitting the application, and also considered the effectiveness of the proposed work plan and budget. The Selection Committee also consulted WP1 about the remaining RDA TIGER budget available for external expert grants and any time constraints the project had for these grants; these consultations were particularly pertinent in the last year of RDA TIGER. The selection process followed the expected procedures laid out in deliverables D1.1 and D6.1.²⁹ Table 3 below provides an overview of the External Expert Grants provided to RDA WGs.

<i>Table 3: RDA TIGER External Expert Grants</i>			
* - Total number of applications includes resubmissions			
** - External Expert Grant awarded but not used by the RDA WG			
Open Call Deadline	Number of applications for External Expert Grants	Number of External Expert Grants awarded by the Selection Committee	RDA WGs receiving External Expert Grants
May 2023	0	0	n/a
August 2023	1	1**	FAIR Data Maturity Model WG**
November 2023	1	1	Data Granularity WG
February 2024	0	0	n/a
May 2024	0	0	n/a
August 2024	2	2	FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG, Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration WG
November 2024	3	1	FAIR Mappings WG
February 2025	2	2	Harmonised terminologies and

²⁹ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 10; D6.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218371>, pp. 23-24. For the end of the project overview and evaluation of Selection Committee procedures, see D6.5 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877446>). See also: Saldner, S., O'Connor, R., Delipalta, A., Asmi, A., Rettberg, N., Lehtsalu, L., & Heikkurinen, M. (2025). RDA TIGER Support Services: Application forms, evaluation forms, scoring sheets (1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734784>

Table 3: RDA TIGER External Expert Grants

* - Total number of applications includes resubmissions

** - External Expert Grant awarded but not used by the RDA WG

			schemas for FAIR metadata in material science and related domains WG, Building Immune Digital Twins WG
May 2025	1	0	n/a
August 2025	2	2	Complex Citations WG, Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration WG
Totals	12*	9 (includes **)	8 (includes **) RDA WGs supported

The experts to carry out the work were chosen either by the Selection Committee when the application materials named an expert and their suitability was assessed as part of the overall assessment of the application, or through open calls for experts published on the RDA website and via RDA TIGER and RDA social media channels. The Selection Committee also directed WP1 to proceed with an open call for experts when they considered the application as a whole fundable but had reservations about the expert named in the application. When needed, the open calls were developed and managed by relevant RDA WGs with the guidance and support of RDA TIGER Facilitation Service (WP5) and WP1, as well as WP2 for the communication of the open calls. The RDA WG selected external experts based on the selection criteria outlined in the open calls. Annex 1 links to the Open Call for External Experts for the RDA FAIR Mappings WG as an example. RDA TIGER published 4 open calls for external experts; other External Expert Grants were awarded to experts named in their applications by RDA WGs.

RDA TIGER WP1 managed External Expert Grants as subcontracting between RDA Association AISBL and the selected experts. The RDA WG that received the External Expert Grant provided WP1 with defined the milestones, deliverables and quality control measures for the subcontract. WP1 used a standard subcontract template³⁰ to draw up subcontracts with external experts (see also Annex 1). The external experts delivered the work according to the work plan established in the contract; the quality control and timeline for delivery was tracked and confirmed by the RDA WG in line with the quality control measures defined in the subcontract. The subcontract was considered complete, and the final payment to the external expert released, once the RDA WG co-chairs had approved the final deliverable(s)

³⁰ RDA TIGER Direct and External Support Mechanisms Supporting Documentation.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431> Note that the included template is the final template and contracts were refined during the project lifetime based on expert advice received by RDA Association AISBL.

expected of the external expert in writing to WP1, following the procedures defined in the subcontract.

These management procedures largely map onto the expected procedure as defined in deliverable D1.1³¹, with two notable exceptions. First, when an open call for external experts was launched publicly, the selection of the external expert was completed by the co-chairs of the RDA WG that received the grant, based on the criteria indicated in the open call for external experts. RDA TIGER WP1 and the Facilitation Service (WP5) supported the call text development and verified the call text before its publication by the Communication Service (WP2). Moreover, a facilitator (WP5) was present at co-chairs' deliberation of the external expert applications received in order to verify the process. But neither WP1 (RDA Association AISBL) nor the Facilitation Service decided the expert selection. Second, the implementation of subcontracts saw close collaboration between the subcontractors and the RDA WGs that received their support and communication between the subcontractors and the RDA WGs did not always, or even predominately, happen through RDA Association AISBL but rather in the form of direct communication. These two exceptions are justified as the WG co-chairs are the experts in the field and are therefore the most suitable parties to assess whether a given person is able to carry out the required work, consult during the contract period and communicate regarding progress; the RDA TIGER project aim was to facilitate and support the WG processes, but not to provide subject matter expertise (which in all cases was not expertise held by the consortium, given the range of niche topics covered).

3.1.2 Impact of External Expert Grants

The External Expert Grants supported RDA WGs with the delivery, testing and validation of their outputs and supported the adoption of WG outputs. The following list provides an overview of the types of activities external experts completed for RDA WGs:

- RDA Data Granularity WG: writing up of the group's final recommendations and formatting of the supporting documentation³²;
- RDA FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG: developing a use case for a hack-a-thon event³³ to support testing and evaluation of the group's final recommendations, providing documentation of the use case³⁴ to further its real world applicability and adoptability;
- RDA Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration WG: developing an interactive catalog dashboard³⁵ to allow users to browse existing standards and submit new ones

³¹ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 11.

³² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-granularity-wg/outputs/>

³³ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2024/blob/main/31.md>

³⁴ <https://github.com/fairtracks/biohackathon-2024-project-31/blob/main/notebooks/case-study.md>

³⁵ <https://rda-moms.github.io/Dashboard/>

in order to support standards discovery and adoption in the multi-omics domain (two external expert grants);

- RDA FAIR Mappings WG: developing and documenting the technical workflow for the group³⁶ in order to support the group's ability to effectively collect and analyse existing mappings and extending existing ontologies and metadata standards based on the group's outputs in order to support the real world adoption of these outputs;
- RDA Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR metadata in material science and related domains WG: completing desk-research and interviews to deliver recommendations for materials schema with reference to DCAT-AP and Schema.org implementation pathways³⁷ in order to support relevance and adoption of the group's outputs;
- Building Immune Digital Twins WG: designing options for the user interface of the group's digital portal³⁸ to facilitate greater adoption of the digital portal;
- Complex Citations WG: organising a hack-a-thon³⁹ with IPCC use case providers and providing a complex citation plan for discussion at the IPCC AR7's First Lead Author Meeting in order to support relevance and community-alignment of the group's output.

As the list above evidences, RDA TIGER External Expert Grants allowed the RDA WGs that received this support to deliver their outputs more efficiently, to test and validate outputs with target users, and to develop tools and platforms that support the adoption and sustainability of WG outputs. The subcontracted external experts contributed technical skills and expertise not available within the RDA TIGER consortium. As such, the External Expert Grants increased the efficiency of the supported RDA WGs and maximised the impact of their outputs, including facilitating the broader adoption of these outputs by users and, by extension, across European and global Open Science communities.

3.1.3 Lessons Learned: External Expert Grants

The RDA TIGER project drew several lessons learned from administrating the external expert grants. These lessons learned related both to the administration of these grants by RDA TIGER as well as the impact of the awarded grants on the RDA WGs:

- **RDA WGs seek funding to increase output adoption** – RDA WGs actively applied for external expert grants, in particular in the last 18 months of RDA TIGER. This

³⁶ The results of this project and all the relevant documentation produced are available on github <https://github.com/mapping-commons/rda-fair-mappings/blob/main/CONTRIBUTING.md>

³⁷ Roscioni, O. M., & Goldbeck, G. (2025). Metadata for cataloguing datasets from materials science and related domains. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949060>

³⁸ RDA Building Immune Digital Twins WG received a RDA TIGER Cascade Grant for Adoption to develop and deliver this digital portal. See p. 23.

³⁹

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/research-data-alliance_cco-hackathon-20-november-2025-13-cet-activity-7395057608547598336-Qdk0?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAPcmEcB9vFvcUUYCq2FKNJJtyy6m39nJzc

highlights that RDA WGs actively seek for support that can help them complete distinct, specialised tasks and increase the adoption of their outputs.

- **RDA WGs seek funding to hire technical expertise** – RDA WGs used the grants to test and validate outputs and to develop technical solutions that supported adoption. The effective delivery of such activities necessitated technical skills and expertise that was not available within the RDA TIGER consortium. This highlights the need that RDA WGs have at times for custom-built technical solutions to develop, test and support the adoption of their outputs. RDA would benefit from funding to have the ability to make such technical skill and expertise available to RDA WGs.
- **The project relied on WG co-chair expertise when working with external experts** – The procedures for External Expert Grants proposed in deliverable D1.1⁴⁰ were largely implemented in the course of the project. The greatest difference emerged in the involvement of RDA WGs in the development and management of open calls for external experts, when such calls were necessary, and in their active engagement in the monitoring of subcontract delivery. This was deemed necessary because the subcontracted work had to align with, and contribute to, the ongoing work in the RDA WGs and RDA WG co-chairs – who applied for the External Expert Grants for their WGs and who WP1 liaised with to prepare and monitor the subcontracts – understood best how the subcontracted work fit in the overall work plan of the WG to deliver greatest impact. The WG co-chairs were also the experts in the field and therefore the most suitable parties to assess both potential candidates to deliver the external expert subcontracts as well as the work delivered by the selected external experts.
- **Managing subcontracting is time intensive** – The distinction between WG co-chairs being the subject matter experts and the project administering the subcontracts created a complex communication structure, where the WP1 required frequent consultations and clarifications on task definitions by the co-chairs, often resulting in a time intensive process. The time it takes to manage subcontracts must be considered well in any similar future projects.

3.2 Financial Support to Third Parties

RDA TIGER also used the Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) mechanism, also known as cascade grants. RDA TIGER GA defined the FSTP mechanism as supporting RDA WGs with development, harmonisation and alignment activities; more specifically, eligible actions included activities in support of the main activities of RDA WGs (e.g. landscape analysis,

⁴⁰ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 11.

survey development, technical harmonisation, report writing) and activities that supported the adoption of RDA WG outputs.⁴¹

The project prepared and published two calls for FSTP. The first call, published on the EC Funding & Tenders Portal in October 2024, was open to individuals and legal entities which sought to develop projects that either supported activities of a RDA WG or the adoption or standardisation of the outputs of RDA WGs.⁴² The second call, published on the EC Funding & Tenders Portal in February 2025 was open to individuals and legal entities which sought to adopt the outputs of RDA WGs.⁴³ In accordance with the EC procedures for FSTP⁴⁴ and the procedure laid out in deliverable D1.1⁴⁵, the calls were defined by WP1 in line with the RDA TIGER GA and submitted to the EC Funding and Tenders portal in coordination with the EC Project Officer assigned to RDA TIGER. According to D1.1 and D6.1, the call texts also had to be reviewed by the Selection Committee⁴⁶; given the volunteer nature of the SC, a subset of Selection Committee members, rather than the full Selection Committee, reviewed call texts. Once finalised, the call texts were inserted in the EC Funding & Tenders Portal by WP1, published in coordination with the EC Project Officer assigned to RDA TIGER, and kept open for 2 months. Both calls texts were also published on the RDA TIGER website which served as the main location for the application process (see also Annex 1)⁴⁷; also the EC Funding & Tenders portal directed users back to the RDA TIGER website to download application materials and submit applications. The call texts on the RDA TIGER website were widely publicised via RDA TIGER beneficiaries social media channels and newsletters. Moreover, an informational webinar was organised for each call to present the aim and objectives of the calls as well as the application and evaluation procedures, and to address any questions from potential applicants.⁴⁸

⁴¹ RDA TIGER GA 101094406, Part B, p. 27-28.

⁴²

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/competitive-calls-cs/9068?order=DESC&pageNumber=2&pageSize=100&sortBy=startDate&isExactMatch=true&type=8&status=31094503&frameworkProgramme=43108390>

⁴³

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/competitive-calls-cs/10283?isExactMatch=true&status=31094501,31094502&frameworkProgramme=43108390&type=8&order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=100&sortBy=startDate>

⁴⁴ EC procedure for FSTP, also followed by RDA TIGER:

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/spaces/IT/pages/25559615/Cascade+Funding+Calls+Financial+Support+for+Third+Parties+FSTP>

⁴⁵ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 12.

⁴⁶ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 12; D6.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218371>, p. 7.

⁴⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger-cascade-grants/> and

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/rda-tiger-cascade-grants-2025/>

⁴⁸ See <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-tiger-cascade-grants-informational-webinar/> and <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-tiger-cascading-grants-informational-webinar-2025/>

The applications received were evaluated by the RDA TIGER Selection Committee, in line with the standard Selection Committee procedures for third party grants, which prioritised evaluation of impact, as foreseen in D6.1⁴⁹. Table 4 below provides an overview of the FSTP grants provided by RDA TIGER:

<i>Table 4: RDA TIGER Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP)</i>				
Call	Number of Applications	Number of FSTP awarded	Countries of FSTP Beneficiaries	RDA WGs referenced in FSTP projects
1st Call	14	3	Sweden, Belgium, the Netherlands	RDA PRO4RS WG, RDA GORC International Model WG, RDA GORC International Implementations WG, RDA Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG, RDA AIDV WG
2nd Call	21	4	France, Ireland, Romania, Serbia	RDA Building Immune Digital Twins WG, RDA National PID Strategies WG, RDA Data Granularity WG, RDA Research Metadata Schemas WG, RDA Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework WG
Totals	35	7	7	10

The FSTP calls were developed and grants managed in line with the Horizon Europe rules for FSTP and Annex A of the RDA TIGER GA. The 1st call made 100,000.00 euro available; the 2nd call made 50,000.00 euro available. According to Annex A, eligible costs included personnel costs (including subcontracting), travel costs, and other costs.⁵⁰ RDA WP1 prepared RDA TIGER Cascade Grant Subaward Agreements⁵¹ with beneficiaries selected by the Selection Committee (see also Annex 1). The template was adapted from previous contracts developed for the specific purpose of FSTP grant mechanisms, and reviewed before use for eligibility and correctness in line with Horizon Europe regulations by a

⁴⁹ D6.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218371>, p. 23.

⁵⁰ RDA TIGER GA 101094406, Part B, p. 28.

⁵¹ RDA TIGER Direct and External Support Mechanisms Supporting Documentation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431>

certified auditor instructed by WP1. Each successful grantee was assessed for eligibility to receive the grant by WP1. Following which, a Cascade Grant Agreement was prepared by WP1 and issued to the successful grantee. In addition, all FSTP beneficiaries received RDA TIGER Cascade Grant Information Sheets⁵² that clarified the support measure and responsibilities of the beneficiaries (see also Annex 1). During grant implementation, WP1 engaged with grantees about mid-term reports and responded to ongoing questions the grantees had about their project management in line with FSTP rules and the RDA TIGER GA.

3.2.1 Impact of Financial Support to Third Parties

The FSTP support measure fostered organisation, national and international level implementations of specific RDA Recommendations and Outputs as well as European and global engagement in support of RDA WG activities. The FSTP projects facilitated the activities and/or adoption of the outputs of 10 RDA Working Groups. The FSTP projects benefitted organisations in 7 countries.

Below, we consider the impact of each of the 7 FSTP projects funded by RDA TIGER.

The FSTP projects that received funding from the 1st Call included:

1. Interactive Web Interface for GORC International Model (lead beneficiary: Uppsala University, Sweden) – the project created an interactive web interface⁵³ for the GORC International Model developed by the RDA Global Open Research Commons International Model WG. The web interface was designed to host also the GORC International Model implementation profiles currently being developed by the RDA GORC International Implementations WG and RDA Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG. The project supported the dissemination and exploitation of outputs from 3 RDA WGs, supporting users within and beyond RDA in navigating and adopting the groups' outputs.
2. Developing an advanced and secure environment for data visitation across RDA (lead beneficiary: Good Clinical Practice Alliance, Belgium) – the project built practical applications based on the outputs of the RDA AIDV WG. More specifically, the project applied AIDV WG outputs to an existing data visitation platform FAIRlyz⁵⁴ and thus supported the adoption of RDA AIDV WG outputs. The project also included a community engagement component; it defined specific roles for RDA members and interested professionals beyond the RDA and invited their active participation in the

⁵² RDA TIGER Direct and External Support Mechanisms Supporting Documentation.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431>

⁵³ [GitHub - NBISweden/rda-gorc-im: GORC International Model visualisation](#) The system deploys through the Docker file or from GitHub pages through GitHub actions.

⁵⁴ <https://www.fairlyz.com/>

project. Outputs included extensive documentation development⁵⁵, guidelines for Internal Review Boards⁵⁶ and Informed Consent Forms⁵⁷, and a white paper on data visitation and biomedical research platforms⁵⁸. The project thus facilitated awareness raising around RDA AIDV WG outputs and their testing and adoption by the relevant communities.

3. Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (lead beneficiary: Maastricht University, the Netherlands) – the project contributed to the ongoing activities of the RDA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS) WG, permitting the WG to expand ongoing activities. The project activities contributed to the expansion of the group’s database of institutional research software policies⁵⁹, development of publications⁶⁰, and workshops aimed at increasing the adoption of the group’s outputs⁶¹.

The FSTP projects that received funding from the 2nd Call included:

1. Digital Platform for the Building Immune Digital Twins (BIDT) WG (lead beneficiary: University of Toulouse, France) – the project developed a functional prototype digital platform⁶² that serves as a central entrypoint to the resources developed by the RDA BIDT WG, including a curated models repository, metadata catalogue, and guidelines and best practices for immune digital twins development and implementation. The project supported the adoption of RDA BIDT WG outputs by the relevant disciplinary community at international level.

⁵⁵ [FAIRlyz User Guide - FAIRLYZ Knowledge Base](#)

⁵⁶ Buendia, P., & Kim, S. (2025). Adding Data Visitation Language to an IRB protocol (1.1c). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00142>

⁵⁷ Buendia, P., & Kim, S. (2025). Adding Data Visitation language to ICFs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00143>

⁵⁸ Buendia, P., Kim, S., Meyers, N., Crawley, F. P., Farrell, G., & Purian, R. (2025). Geographies of Trust: AI, Biomedicine, and the Next Era of Federated and Visiting Data Models (1.1c). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17703266>

⁵⁹ <https://www.researchsoft.org/institutional-policies/>

⁶⁰ Barker, M., Hernández Serrano, P. V., Rudmann, D., & Martínez-Ortiz, C. (2025). Case studies of implementation of policies that support research software in research organisations (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16919320>; Hernández Serrano, P. V., Barker, M., Katz, D. S., Martínez-Ortiz, C., & Shanahan, H. (2025). Identifying Gaps in Research Software Policy: A report from Subgroup 3/4 of the ReSA & RDA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS) Working Group (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16941858>

⁶¹ Workshops included PRO4RS WG session at the RDA Plenary 25 meeting in Brisbane, Australia, 13-16 October 2025 (https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-resa-policies-research-organisations-research-software-pro4rs/plenary-participation/?application_id=188141), a presentation at the New Zealand Research Software Engineering Conference on 23-24 September 2025 (<https://www.rseconference.nz/programme/>), and a presentation at the RDA Netherlands Meet-Up on 3 September 2025 (<https://lcrdm.nl/evenementen/rda-in-nl-community-meet-up/>).

⁶² Prototype available here <https://bidt-demo-6ea7c47f5a57.herokuapp.com/> (accessed 15.12.2025).

2. EOSC Compatible National PID Strategies (lead beneficiary: Royal Irish Academy, Ireland) – the project developed a national PID recommendation for Ireland. The project built on the recommendations of the RDA National PID Strategies WG⁶³, and aligned these with outputs from HORIZON-INFRA projects FAIRCORE4EOSC⁶⁴ and FAIR-IMPACT⁶⁵ as well as the EOSC PID Policy⁶⁶. The project completed a gap analysis of the existing Irish national PID strategy⁶⁷ and developed a methodology for assessing existing national PID policies against the EOSC PID Policy⁶⁸ and a EOSC-compatible national PID recommendation for Ireland⁶⁹. The project supported the adoption of RDA National PID Strategies WG Recommendations, and also provided feedback for the follow up work underway within the RDA National PID Strategies IG.
3. Enhancing Machine-Actionability of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library through FAIR Mappings and Metadata Alignment (lead beneficiary: National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics, Romania) – the project enhanced the semantic interoperability of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library⁷⁰ by implementing the Recommendations by the RDA Data Granularity WG⁷¹ and RDA Research Metadata Schemas WG⁷². Documentation of the project was published.⁷³ The project supported the adoption of the Recommendations of two RDA WGs at repository level, also supporting the alignment of the repository with the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁷⁴.

⁶³ Brown, C., Simons, N., Bangert, D., & Sadler, S. (2023). RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

⁶⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

⁶⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁶⁶ Buys, M., Dreyer, B., Hellström, M., Kálmán, T., Mejias, G., Parkoła, T., Růžička, M., & Suominen, T. (2024). Community-specific (and stakeholder category-specific) perspectives on the EOSC PID architecture and the EOSC PID policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11396803>

⁶⁷ Doran, M., & O'Neill, J. (2025). D2.1 Gap Analysis Between Ireland's PID Strategy and the EOSC PID Policy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17700383>

⁶⁸ Doran, M., & O'Neill, J. (2025). D3.2 Reusable methodology and template for national EOSC-aligned PID Strategies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17723434>

⁶⁹ Doran, M., & O'Neill, J. (2025). D4.2 EOSC Compatible National PID Recommendation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17721148>

⁷⁰ <https://infraart.inoe.ro/>

⁷¹ Jenkyns, R., Mathiak, B., McNeill, K., Smith, G., Sun, G., Little, C., Jones, B., Elbert, D., Hellström, M., Schabinger, R., & RDA Data Granularity WG. (2025). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

⁷² Wu, M., Juty, N., RDA Research Metadata Schemas WG, Collins, J., Duerr, R., Ridsdale, C., Shepherd, A., Verhey, C., & Castro, L. J. (2021). Guidelines for publishing structured metadata on the web (3.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00066>

⁷³ Cortea, I. M. (2025). Semantic Artefact Documentation for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library Datasets and Data Catalog (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17570835>

⁷⁴ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/service/eosc-execution-framework>

4. Enhancing Scholarly Knowledge Graph Interoperability through SKG-IF Integration in TeslaRIS (lead beneficiary: University of Novi Sad, Serbia) – the project enhanced interoperability between scholarly knowledge graph systems by integrating the outputs of the RDA Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework WG⁷⁵ in TeslaRIS⁷⁶, the research information system in the University of Novi Sad. Documentation of the project was published.⁷⁷ The project supported the adoption of RDA Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework WG outputs at the level of an open source current research information system platform, enabling interoperability of research outputs and providing a use case that can support further adoption.

The selected and implemented FSTP projects fulfilled the aim set out in the RDA TIGER GA for the FSTP mechanism: the projects supported RDA WGs with development, harmonisation and alignment activities as well as supported the adoption of RDA WG outputs.⁷⁸ The adoption of RDA outputs was supported at organisation, national and international level, enabling organisations and national bodies to improve interoperability and alignment with relevant EOSC frameworks and supporting domain communities in accessing and adopting relevant RDA WG outputs. One of the WGs - RDA PRO4RS WG - used FSTP to expand and enhance ongoing work within the WG by ensuring dedicated staff time for the development of the group's outputs.

3.2.2 Lessons Learned: Financial Support to Third Parties

The RDA TIGER project drew several lessons learned from administrating the FSTP mechanism:

- **Selection Committee's engagement with highly ranked applicants improves clarity and focus of the selected FSTP projects** – The number of applications ranked highly by the Selection Committee necessitated the Selection Committee to suggest proposed budget adjustments to applicants in both FSTP rounds in order to accept more proposals; this was also necessary because in most cases applicants opted to request the full budget on offer (the call texts indicated a budget range, not the exact budget available, see Annex 1). The applicants received the suggestions for adjusted budgets positively and all these highly ranked projects proceeded to implementation. Overall, the Selection Committee's approach resulted in more FSTP projects being

⁷⁵ <https://skg-if.github.io/>

⁷⁶ <https://testcris.uns.ac.rs/index.jsf>

⁷⁷ <https://github.com/sci2zero/TeslaRIS-backend/wiki/Crosswalks> and <https://github.com/sci2zero/TeslaRIS-backend/wiki/SKG%E2%80%90API#supported-filters>

⁷⁸ RDA TIGER GA 101094406, Part B, p. 27-28.

funded and the funded projects were more clearly defined and focused, resulting in higher quality cascade grants.

- **Applicants need support to identify relevant RDA Recommendations to adopt** – In the case of adoption grants, the applicants/ grantees at times needed support to refine which RDA Recommendations and outputs they can realistically implement within the time and financial constraints of a FSTP project, but also in terms of suitability to their particular case. The Selection Committee provided applicants feedback to this end.
- **Identifying the beneficiary of a FSTP grant awarded to a RDA WG should be determined in the application phase** – RDA WGs have multiple co-chairs. In many cases, a FSTP application was co-developed by several co-chairs and submitted on behalf of the WG. For successful applications, in some cases, selecting which co-chair can act as the beneficiary for the FSTP grant was complicated because of different administrative procedures across different European institutions. This led to some extra administrative effort. In the future, we would consider asking applicants to identify and confirm the potential beneficiary already in the application phase.
- **The value of engagement with RDA WGs is not always recognised by RDA members' organisations** – For one successful application, the first intended beneficiary rejected the grant because the organisation did not consider the grant of explicit benefit to itself, but rather as something that benefitted an RDA WG. The project was only able to go ahead once the WG co-chairs identified another host institution (beneficiary) for the FSTP project. This highlighted that for some organisations the value of the engagement of their researchers and staff in RDA may not be fully recognised.
- **FSTP is a complex mechanism, and requires the beneficiary to have expertise in administering EC grants** – The complexities in the administration of a FSTP grant resulted in some grantees seeking detailed input and advice from WP1 on the administration, management and financial eligibility conditions and cost activities within their grant. The time it takes to manage FSTP grants by the WP responsible for them in the project must be considered well in any similar future projects.
- **Dedicated calls for cascade grants (FSTP) provided a more streamlined application process and should have been opened earlier in the project lifecycle** – As part of the initial project plan, WP1 had intended to launch calls for the FSTP mechanism in response to applications under the continuously open RDA TIGER Open Call (see Annex 1). The intended process was for WGs to request support for large funded projects; this request would then be evaluated by the Selection Committee and subsequently the project would draft and publish a call for FSTP in collaboration with

the successful applicant WG.⁷⁹ No such applications were received by the project via the Open Call in the first 18 months of the project. As a result, and to ensure that FSTP grants would be offered to the community as intended, the project launched the open first call under the FSTP mechanism in October 2024 and the second one in February 2025. This lack of applications in the first intended process via the RDA TIGER Open Call created a time pressure in an already complex and time intensive process that put additional administrative burden on WP1. Retrospectively, the pivot to dedicated RDA TIGER Cascade Grant calls should have happened earlier in the project lifecycle.

4. Key Lessons Learned from Direct and External Support Provision

The key lessons learned from providing direct and external support through RDA TIGER can be divided into two: support administration/ management lessons learned and RDA WG focused lessons learned:

Key support administration/ management lessons learned:

- Managing a broad range of different types of direct and external support places administrative demand on a project. In RDA TIGER, the management of direct and external support was part of the activities of WP1. While the effort was adequately planned within the project, and the processes streamlined thanks to the use of templates and clear information sheets for support recipients, in future projects with numerous direct and external support mechanisms that necessitate the development and management of a number of reimbursements, subcontracts and FSTPs (i.e. cascade grants), effort needs to be carefully planned. In RDA TIGER, the management of these support mechanisms also fell mostly in the second half of the project (for reasons discussed above on p. 26); in future projects, care should be taken to distribute effort better across the work plan.
- In the administration of the FSTP mechanism, WP1 had to contend with differing administrative procedures and time-frames across FSTP beneficiary institutions across Europe. Awareness, knowledge and ability to engage with different institutional realities while administering the FSTP mechanism uniformly and coherently, and in line with the EC and RDA TIGER GA rules, was necessary.
- WP1 recognised that it needed to engage the Selection Committee and RDA WG co-chairs to administer the external support mechanisms effectively, at times also adjusting the procedures proposed in D1.1 at the beginning of the project (see above on pp. 19, 25). The project recognised the expertise of the Selection Committee and the RDA WG co-chairs applying for external support; involving them more extensively

⁷⁹ D1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>, p. 12.

than initially foreseen ensured that the resulting grants were more efficient and delivered greater potential impact.

Key RDA WG focused lessons learned:

- Individuals and organisations applying for adoption grants (FSTP mechanism) at times needed support in defining which RDA Recommendations and Outputs are most suitable for their intended projects. This indicates the need for continued awareness raising about RDA Recommendations and Outputs, including about the ways in which RDA WG outputs can be adopted. RDA Adoption Stories⁸⁰ are key to this.
- RDA WGs applied for support by external experts to test and validate outputs and to develop technical solutions in support of adoption. They sought technical skills and expertise not available within the groups, either because of lack of specific specialised skills or because of the lack of capacity of the volunteer-based membership. This highlighted the need that RDA WGs often have for custom-built technical solutions. RDA would benefit from funding to have the ability to make such technical skill and capacity available to RDA WGs in order to support testing and adoption of RDA outputs.
- The broad-based interest in travel grants from RDA active members in WGs and IGs, in Europe and across the globe, highlights keen interest of RDA Members in participating in RDA working meetings. We also note, however, that RDA members, who mostly engage with RDA as volunteers, eagerly seek out available funding opportunities to support their engagement with RDA.

5. Impact of Direct and External Support Provision

The Research Data Alliance is a community of over 16,000 members globally that since 2013 has produced 160 Recommendations and Outputs⁸¹. This expertise and wealth of outputs is free and open to all, available for adoption. It is also based on volunteer effort and contributions from experts around the world that often contribute outside their main jobs. The support provided to the RDA WGs by RDA TIGER through direct and external support mechanisms has supported RDA WG members in travelling to and organising WG meetings to permit more effective development of their group's outputs, or the adoption of those outputs. The external support mechanisms have also permitted RDA WGs to benefit from the skills and effort of subcontracted external experts to develop specific activities or outputs for the WGs; moreover RDA WGs have seen their Recommendations and outputs adopted in various institutional, national, European and international settings. The adoption

⁸⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/>

⁸¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/>

grants provided through the FSTP mechanism furthermore generated valuable examples of adoption that are available for replication. Overall, RDA TIGER awarded 32 different direct and external support grants (Table 1) that benefitted 19 RDA WGs (Tables 2, 3, 4). Through these support mechanisms, RDA WGs were able to increase their efficiency and to maximise the impact of their outputs on the European Open Science Cloud, global Open Science practices, and researchers, data professionals and the society at large.

Annex 1: Links to Direct and External Support Mechanisms Documentation

RDA TIGER Open Call text	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431 Also: https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rd-a-tiger/open-call-rda-working-group-facilitation-support/
RDA TIGER Open Call Application Form	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734784
1st Call for RDA TIGER Travel Grants	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
2nd Call for RDA TIGER Travel Grants	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
RDA TIGER Travel Grants application form	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734784
Information Sheet for RDA TIGER Travel Grant recipients (1st Call)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
Information Sheet for RDA TIGER Travel Grant recipients (2nd Call)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
Template - RDA TIGER Travel Grant Reimbursement Agreement	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
An exemplar RDA TIGER Call for External Experts (RDA FAIR Mappings WG)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
Template - RDA TIGER Subcontract Agreement for External Experts	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
RDA TIGER Cascade Grants Call 2024 (1st call)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431 Also: https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger-cascade-grants/
RDA TIGER Cascade Grants Call 2025 (2nd call)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431 Also: https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rd-a-tiger/rda-tiger-cascade-grants-2025/
RDA TIGER Cascade Grants Information Sheet for Grantees (1st call)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
RDA TIGER Cascade Grants Information Sheet for Grantees (2nd call)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431

Template - RDA TIGER Cascade Grants Subaward Agreement

https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17896431
